

ON THE AMINO-ACIDS CONTENT OF LIVER PREPARATIONS

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The amino-acids as present in liver remain almost unchanged in a liver preparation made by enzymatic hydrolysis. The latter also promotes a better growth for *Lactobacillus casei* and is considered to be a better therapeutic medicament in cases where liver is indicated.

With the recent progress in the Science of nutrition, a food is no longer being taken for granted, but is actually used as a specific therapeutic measure in the treatment of disease. Liver is used as food and medicine for various purposes. Being rich in protein, minerals and vitamins, it is being found to be specially valuable in certain types of anaemia. In spite of its wider use, the active principles that are responsible for its therapeutic importance are not exactly known. Jacobson and Subbarow (*J. Clin. Invest.*, 1937, 16, 573) have shown that *L*-tyrosine that is present in liver does not play any part but this with incorporation of other factor, which is of a polypeptide nature, enhances the physiological property of liver in pernicious anaemia. A most recent addition to the group of purified nutritional substances is the use of a mixture of various essential amino-acids as a source of protein food. Liver would accordingly be better utilised, if its protein be fractionated to its component parts by suitable hydrolysis. As a matter of fact, a proteolysed liver preparation (*cf.* Davis, Davidson, Riding and Shaw, *Brit. Med. J.*, 1943, i, 656) containing fragmented molecules of liver protein along with its accessory growth factors, is being found to be superior in the treatment of various types of anaemias. Mapson (*Biochem. J.*, 1932, 26, 970) has shown that the papain-digested liver contains almost all the growth stimulating factors of the whole liver; whereas these vary again in fractionated preparations. But as most of the preparations are still obtained either by B. P. method or from Cohn's Fraction G, it is considered to be of interest to study the various amino-acids, present in liver, — raw, proteolysed, Cohn Fraction G, and *Extractum Hepatis Siccum*, B. P. The results of the investigations that have so far been carried out have been embodied in the experimental part of this paper. For simplicity and ready availability beef liver was taken for the above study.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fresh beef liver was collected from the local slaughter house. A part of it was minced and dried to a constant weight and this was regarded as whole liver in the paper. Raw liver was used for the preparation of proteolysed liver according to Davis *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), Cohn's fraction G (*cf.* Cohn *et al.*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1928, 77, 325), and *Extractum Hepatis Siccum* (B. P. 1932).

The amino-acids as present in all the above liver preparations were determined. The diamino-acids, histidine, arginine and lysine were estimated according to Kossel and Kutscher (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1900, 31, 165) and the amino-acids, tryptophane (Horn and Jones, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1945, 157, 154), methionine (Macarthy and Sullivan, *J. Biol.*

Chem., 1941, 141, 871) and tyrosine (Weiss, *Biochem. Z.*, 1919, 97, 170) were estimated by colorimetric procedure using Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter. The results have been recorded on the basis of the dry powder in Table I.

TABLE I

Preparations.	Dry solid per 100 g. of raw liver.	Total protein on dry basis.	Percentage expressed on total protein.					
			Histidine.	Arginine.	Lysine.	Tyrosine.	Tryptophane.	Methionine
Whole liver	27.5	67.27%	1.89%	5.9%	4.2%	3.3%	0.98%	4.0%
Proteolysed liver	18.7	75.9	2.1	5.6	4.8	3.0	1.2	3.5
Cohn's Fraction 'G'	1.24	80.37	1.66	3.85	7.6	1.3	1.08	1.3
<i>Extractum Hepatis Siccum</i>	2.88	46.68	4.6	1.07	10.3	1.1	Trace	3.6

Growth factors of proteolysed liver and fractionated liver preparations were determined by estimating the acid produced by the growth of *Lactobacillus casei* according to the method of Snell and Strong (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1939, 11, 346). The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Formation of acid from various preparations of liver

Results expressed as total number of c. c. of 0.1N-acid produced for 16 c. c. basal medium.

Preparations.	Amts. expressed as % raw liver with respective amount of N ₂ as mg. per cent.							
	1		2		3		4	
	N ₂ .	Acid.	N ₂ .	Acid.	N ₂ .	Acid.	N ₂ .	Acid.
Proteolysed liver	11.39	1.6	22.78	2.0	45.56	2.4	91.12	2.8
Aqueous extract of liver	5.37	1.4	10.74	1.60	21.48	1.6	42.96	1.8
Cohn's Fraction 'G'	1.59	0.2	3.18	0.40	6.36	0.6	12.72	0.6

The amount of raw liver in each preparation being the same, percentage of nitrogen and growth factors are highest in the proteolysed liver.

DISCUSSION

It may be noticed from Table I that the amino-acid contents of the proteolysed liver preparations are almost of the same order as present in the original liver; whereas

in other preparations their percentages differ appreciably. The tyrosine content of the proteolysed liver is 3.0 % of the total proteinous body, whereas the same in the whole liver is found to be 3.3%. Liver is also a good nutritive substance for the growth of *Lactobacillus casei*. In assaying the different preparations the amount of acid produced in the basal medium by the *Lactobacillus* is found highest where proteolysed liver is used as a nutritive factor (vide Table II). The proteolysed liver is quite effective in small dosage in uncomplicated cases of tropical macrocytic anaemia (cf. Davis *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). The findings in the present investigation tend to indicate that the active physiological principles as present in original liver remain almost unchanged in proteolysed liver preparations, and as such it appears that a proteolysed liver may be a better therapeutic preparation for the treatment of those type of anaemia where liver is indicated (cf. Das-Gupta, Ganguly and Chatterji, *Ind. Med.Gaz.* 1946, 81, 83).

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Received September 13, 1946.
